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BUĞDAY SAPLARINDAN ÜRETİLEN KAĞIT HAMURLARININ FLUTİNG KAĞIT ÜRETİMİNDE DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ

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Özet

Bu çalışmada buğday sapından kimyasal yöntemlerle pişirme yapılarak kağıt hamuru elde edilmiştir. Buğday sapından elde edilen birincil lif kağıt hamuru, ikincil lif olan eski oluklu mukavva kağıt hamurları (EOM) ile belirli oranlarda (%0, %5, %10, %15, %20, %25 ve %30) harmanlanarak 90 ± 4 gramajında fluting kağıtları üretilmiş ve üretilen test kağıtlarının fiziksel ve optik özellikleri tespit edilmiştir. EOM kağıt hamuruna ilave edilen buğday sapı kağıt hamurunun katılım oranının artmasına paralel olarak fluting kağıtların mekanik özelliklerinin olumlu yönde arttığı gözlemlenmiştir. EOM kağıt hamurlarına %30 buğday sapı hamuru ilave edildiğinde fluting kağıtların kopma uzunluğu 3.44 km'den 4.34 km'ye yükselerek yaklaşık %26.2 oranında bir artış meydana gelmiştir. Fluting kağıtların optik özelliklerinde buğday sapı kağıt hamurunun kayda değer bir etkisi olmamıştır. Sonuç olarak, ambalaj kağıdı üretiminde kullanılan fluting kağıtların mekanik özelliklerinin buğday sapı kağıt hamurları ilave edilerek iyileştirilmesi ile hem üretim sırasında meydana gelen kağıt kopma sorunlarının önüne geçilebilir hem de ambalajın fiziksel ve mekaniksel etkilere karşı direnci artırılabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Buğday sapı, fluting kağıt, eski oluklu mukavva, mekanik, optik

Abstract

In this study, pulps were obtained by chemically cooking wheat straw. Fluting papers with a basis weight of 90 ± 4 gsm were produced by blending primary wheat straw pulp with secondary fiber pulp from old corrugated containers (OCC) in various proportions (%0, %5, %10, %15, %20, %25, and %30), and the physical and optical properties of the produced test papers were determined. It was observed that the mechanical properties of fluting papers improved positively as the proportion of wheat straw pulp added to OCC pulp increased. When 30% wheat straw pulp was added to OCC pulp, the breaking length of fluting papers increased from 3.44 km to 4.34 km, indicating an approximately 26.2% increase. The optical properties of fluting papers were not significantly affected by the addition of wheat straw pulp. In conclusion, enhancing the mechanical properties of fluting papers used in packaging paper production by incorporating wheat straw pulp can prevent paper tearing issues during production and enhance the resistance of the packaging to physical and mechanical impacts.

Keywords: Wheat stalk, fluting paper, old corrugated cardboard, mechanics, optics

INTRODUCTION

Fluting papers are typically produced from recyclable corrugated cardboard and packaging paper waste with an efficiency of approximately 85%, undergoing various cleaning and screening stages. Due to their ability to retain shape with heat and moisture, they are utilized as corrugated medium in corrugated cardboard production (Biermann, 1993). In our country, waste papers are commonly used as the raw material source for the production of corrugated cardboard papers. However, the quality and characteristics of waste papers allow them to be recycled only 4-6 times, and during recycling, a phenomenon known as hornification occurs, leading to a decrease in fiber bonding ability and surface area (McKee, 1971; Biermann, 1993; Şahin, 2014). Consequently, the strength properties of the produced papers decrease, making it challenging to achieve desired properties as the number of recycling cycles increases. Therefore, strength-enhancing chemicals are used in the production of corrugated cardboard papers, creating both economic and environmental issues (Clark, 1978; Biermann, 1993; Üner and Şahin, 2004).

Papers obtained from primary quality pulp exhibit higher physical property values compared to papers produced from secondary quality pulp. Primary quality fibers can be obtained from annual plants in agricultural areas or our forest resources. In Turkey, the annual wheat production is approximately 21 million tons, ranking 11th in the world (FAO, 2020). According to studies and agricultural experts, approximately 2 kg of wheat straw is obtained from the production location of 1 kg of wheat (Akgül, 1997; Çiçekler, 2012; Tutus and Çiçekler, 2016). Consequently, around 42 million tons of wheat straw are produced annually in our country. However, considering the 15% losses during baling and transportation and 17% losses due to stubbles on the soil, there is approximately a 32% overall loss. In summary, about 68% of the 42 million tons of wheat straw, i.e., 28.6 million tons, can be utilized.

According to the data from the General Directorate of Forestry, there is a total forest area of 22,933,000 hectares in Turkey in 2020 (Anonymous, 2021). Oak, a deciduous tree species, ranks first with 5.8 million hectares, followed by red pine, a coniferous tree species, with 5.6 million hectares. Worldwide, forest areas have decreased from 32.5% to 30.8% between 1990 and 2020, equivalent to an area of 178 million hectares (approximately the size of Libya). Despite these reductions, with the implementation of strategic plans in some countries and the establishment of new forests, forest losses have decreased from 7.84 million hectares per year to 4.74 million hectares. The main cause of forest loss is attributed to the expansion of agricultural lands to meet the increasing food demands of the growing population (FAO, 2020).

In this study, unbleached pulps obtained from wheat straws were blended with old corrugated cardboard in certain ratios to produce fluting papers. The effects of adding wheat straw pulps to old corrugated cardboard pulps in

specific proportions on the physical properties of fluting papers were investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study, wheat straws and old corrugated cardboard, which are widely spread across agricultural areas in our country, were utilized as lignocellulosic raw materials. During the wheat straw selection process for the experiment, samples were collected to represent the entire agricultural area. The cooking conditions applied to wheat straws are provided in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Soda-Air-KBH₄ Cooking Conditions Applied to Wheat Straws

NaOH charge(%)	14
Air pressure (bar)	9
Potassium borohydride (KBH ₄) charge (%)	0,7
Temperature (°C)	140
Time to maximum temperature (min)	40
Time at maximum temperature (min)	50
Liquor to raw material ratio (L/kg)	5/1

Following the cooking process, wheat straw pulps were subjected to washing with abundant water on a 200-mesh sieve to remove cooking chemicals (black liquor). The washed pulps were then opened in a laboratory-type disintegrator for 10 minutes and screened through a shaker sieve with a 0.15 mm aperture to separate the uncooked portions. The old corrugated cardboard (OCC) papers were obtained from Göçdiz Corrugated Cardboard Factory located in the Pazarcık district of Kahramanmaraş in 2014. The corrugated cardboard papers, divided into small pieces, were individually disintegrated into fibers in a laboratory-type Hollander device, adjusted to a consistency of 20-25%, and stored in polyethylene bags at +4 °C.

Table 2. Ratios of Pulps Used in Fluting Paper Production

No	Wheat straw pulp	OCC pulp
Ratios (%)		
1	-	100
2	5	95
3	10	90
4	15	85
5	20	80

6	15	75
7	30	70
8	100	-

Before paper production, wheat straw pulp and OCC paper pulps were beaten in the Hollander beater machine to a freeness degree of 35 ± 3 SR°. Subsequently, they were blended in the ratios specified in Table 2 and used to produce fluting paper. Fluting papers with a basis weight of 90 ± 4 gsm were manufactured using the Rapid Kothen paper machine according to ISO 5269-2 standard. Ten test papers were produced for each experiment mentioned in Table 2. The physical and optical properties of the obtained fluting papers from the experiments were determined using the relevant standards, as listed in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Standards Used for Physical and Optical Tests Applied to Fluting Papers

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Grammage (gr/m^2)	TAPPI T 410 om-88
Thickness (μ)	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Bulkiness (cm^3/gr) and Density (gr/cm^3)	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Breaking length (m)	TAPPI T 494 om-01
Burst index ($\text{kPa m}^2/\text{gr}$)	TAPPI T 403 om-91
CCT (Corrugated Crush Test) (kN.m^{-1})	TAPPI T 824
CMT (Concora Medium Test) (N)	TAPPI T 809
SCT (Short Span Compression) (kN.m^{-1})	TAPPI T 826
Brightness (%ISO)	ISO/DIS 2470
Whiteness (%ISO)	ISO 11475
Opacity (%ISO)	ISO/DIS 2471

The tests mentioned above were repeated five times for each experiment, and a variance analysis and Duncan test were additionally applied to demonstrate the impact of the mixture ratios on the physical and optical properties of the papers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some physical properties of fluting papers produced with mixtures of old corrugated cardboard (OCC) and wheat straw pulps at a basis weight of 90 ± 4 gsm are provided in Table 4. It is observed that the addition of wheat straw pulps in certain ratios improves the physical properties compared to OCC pulps. According to the variance analysis results, it has been determined that the addition of wheat straw pulps to OCC pulps in specific ratios has a significant effect on the tensile strength, burst and tear indices, CMT, CCT, and SCT values of the produced fluting papers.

Table 4. Some Physical Properties of Fluting Papers

Grup No	OCC pulp (%)	Wheat Straw pulp (%)	Breaking length (km)	Tear index (mN.m ² .g)	Burst index (kPa.m ² .g ⁻¹)	CMT (N)	CCT (kN.m ⁻¹)	SCT (kN.m ⁻¹)	Bulkiness (cm ³ .gr ⁻¹)	Density (gr.cm ⁻³)
1	100	-	3.44e	8.30a	2.17d	141a	1.09c	1.91c	1.78	0.56
2	95	5	3.76ed	8.56a	2.54dc	139a	1.11c	1.88c	1.68	0.59
3	90	10	3.90dc	8.17a	2.71cb	153a	1.25cb	2.01cb	1.68	0.60
4	85	15	4.16cb	8.72a	2.80cba	152a	1.27cb	2.27a	1.65	0.61
5	80	20	4.06dcb	8.22a	2.89cba	162a	1.44b	2.20ba	1.66	0.60
6	75	25	4.77a	8.30a	3.22a	163a	1.49ba	2.19ba	1.59	0.63
7	70	30	4.34b	8.38a	3.03ba	182a	1.69a	2.36a	1.61	0.62
8	-	100	7.86	5.20	4.45	268	2.80	3.58	1.31	0.76

** The mean values indicated with the same letters do not show statistically significant differences according to the Duncan test.

The effects of the participation ratios of wheat straw pulp to OCC pulp on some physical properties of fluting papers are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Effects of Wheat Straw Pulp addition Ratio on the Physical Properties of Fluting Papers

The breaking length of papers produced with the addition of wheat straw pulps to OCC pulps is directly proportional to the increase in the wheat straw addition amount. Compared to the control samples, increases of 9.3%, 13.37%, 20.93%, 18.02%, 38.66%, 26.16%, and 128.48% for breaking length, -3.13%, -1.57%, 5.06%, -0.96%, 0%, 0.96%, and -37.35% for the tear index, 17.05%, 24.88%, 29.03%, 33.18%, 48.39%, 39.63%, and 105.07% for the burst index, respectively.

Some optical properties of fluting papers produced from mixtures of OCC and wheat straw pulps are provided in Table.

Table 5. Optical Properties of Fluting Papers

No	OCC pulp (%)	Wheat straw pulp (%)	Whiteness (%ISO)	Brightness (%ISO)	Yellowness (E313)
1	100	0	36.40c	27.83a	35.46a
2	95	5	36.28c	27.54a	36.08b
3	90	10	36.53cb	27.59a	36.49cb
4	85	15	36.72cb	27.60a	36.88c
5	80	20	36.58cb	27.27a	37.61d
6	75	25	37.54a	27.97a	37.6d9
7	70	30	37.24ba	27.52a	38.44e
8	-	100	40.05	26.88	47.25

** The mean values indicated with the same letters do not show statistically significant differences according to the Duncan test.

When examining the optical properties of papers produced with mixtures of OCC and wheat straw pulps, it is observed that as the proportion of wheat straw pulps in the mixture increases, the yellowness values are

adversely affected, while the brightness values show an increase of up to 0.33%, 0.36%, 0.88%, 0.49%, 3.13%, 2.31%, and 10.03%. There is no significant effect of wheat straw pulps on brightness values. In Figure 2, the effects of the participation ratios of wheat straw pulp to OCC pulp on some optical properties of fluting papers are illustrated.

Figure 2. Effects of Wheat Straw Pulp Addition Ratio on the Optical Properties of Fluting Papers

CONCLUSION

In this study, the strength properties of fluting papers produced from recycled old corrugated cardboards are found to be lower than those obtained from wheat straw pulps. Additionally, they exhibit physical properties below the minimum values specified in the TS 12728:2001 standard. Therefore, the market supply and acceptance of fluting papers produced solely from recycled old corrugated cardboards are quite challenging. In this research, unbleached paper pulps obtained from wheat straw were blended with recycled old corrugated cardboards at certain ratios to produce fluting papers. When examining the properties of the produced papers, it was observed that a significant portion of them exceeded the values specified in the relevant standards.

The demand for recycling papers has rapidly increased both in our country and worldwide. However, the paper industry faces a raw material shortage as first-quality paper can only be recycled about 6-7 times with various chemicals, and it cannot provide a sufficient number of products with the desired quality. The conversion of agricultural waste such as wheat straw into paper pulp with eco-friendly chemicals not only supports the paper industry's raw material search but also contributes to the production of paper with the desired properties. Moreover, it reduces the demand for imported paper pulp in our country, thereby contributing to the national economy.

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